

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 134:0 A Song of Ascents.</p> <p>Psa. 134:1 Behold, ^abless the LORD, all ^bservants of the LORD, Who ^{1c}serve ^aby night in the house of the LORD! ² ^aLift up your hands to the ^bsanctuary And bless the LORD. ³ May the LORD ^abless you from Zion, He who ^bmade heaven and earth.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 134:1 שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת תְּנֵה אֲבָרְכוּ</p> <p style="text-align: right;">אֶת־יְהוָה כָּל־עַבְדֵי יְהוָה</p> <p style="text-align: right;">הַעֹמְדִים בְּבֵית־יְהוָה בַּלַּיְלוֹת׃ ²</p> <p style="text-align: right;">שְׂאוּ־יְדַכֶּם קִדְשׁ וּבָרְכוּ אֶת־יְהוָה׃</p> <p style="text-align: right;">יְבָרְכֵנָּה יְהוָה מִצִּיּוֹן עֲשֵׂה שָׁמַיִם ³</p> <p style="text-align: right;">וְאָרֶץ׃</p>

References

Psalm 134:1

¹Lit *stand*

^aPs 103:21

^bPs 135:1, 2

^cDeut 10:8; 1 Chr 23:30; 2 Chr 29:11

^d1 Chr 9:33

Psalm 134:2

^aPs 28:2; 1 Tim 2:8

^bPs 63:2

Psalm 134:3

^aPs 128:5

^bPs 124:8

Targum

Psa. 134:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. Behold, bless the LORD, all servants of the LORD who stand on watch in the sanctuary of the LORD and sing praise at night. ² Lift up your hands, O priests, on the holy dais, and bless the LORD. ³ The LORD will bless you from Zion, he who made heaven and earth.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is the conclusion of the fifteen Psalms of Ascents, which describes how Israel rises higher and closer to the LORD. The Psalmist shares that the priests who serve the Temple in Zion must spread the blessings from the LORD throughout Israel. After the Temple was destroyed, the people suffered in a dark night of exile. It was the priest's job to inspire the people with a message of Divine encouragement.

Notes on this Psalm

If you are a part of a faith community, ask yourself, is your preaching leader inspiring you to worship, praise and serve the LORD. There are persons who are rabbis and ministers who cannot inspire the people. There are numerous tasks for clergy that those who cannot offer inspiring messages of hope in the not be leading the community. A problem today in the church is that fewer persons want to become pastors. This leaves the denominations with a big problem. How does the leaders get pastors in churches? Unfortunately, today they are forced to assign unqualified persons to these positions. All this does is to reduce the spirituality of the congregation. There are bishops who can inspire the people but are consecrated because they “check boxes” opposed to having the LORD’s Shekinah with them. Two problems exist. The first is the lack of persons of God who can inspire the people. The second is the selection of leaders (bishops) by what woke boxes they check off as opposed to their ability to lead. If you have any voice in the decision-making process, it is well pastime to get your voice heard.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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